

ARE MICROBES AWAKE DURING THE POLAR NIGHT?

P.M. Valdespino-Castillo^{1,2}, R.A. Mercado-Juárez^{3,6}, L.A.M. Ruberto^{4,5}, W.P. Mac Cormack^{4,5}, L.I. Falcón⁶, M. Merino-Ibarra⁷, S. Batista⁸, H.-Y. Holman⁹, R.J. Alcántara-Hernández⁹

¹ *Escuela Nacional de Ciencias de la Tierra, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México CDMX, Mexico; valdespinopm@encit.unam.mx;*

² *Molecular Biophysics and Integrated Bioimaging Division, BSISB Program, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, One Cyclotron Rd, Berkeley, USA;*

³ *Posgrado en Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, CDMX, Mexico;*

⁴ *Instituto Antártico Argentino, San Martín, Buenos Aires, Argentina;*

⁵ *Instituto NANOBIOTEC UBA-CONICET, Facultad de Farmacia y Bioquímica, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Junín 956 6to piso CABA, Argentina;*

⁶ *Laboratorio de Ecología Bacteriana, Instituto de Ecología, UNAM, Campus Yucatán, Mexico;*

⁷ *Unidad Académica de Biodiversidad Acuática, Instituto de Ciencias del Mar y Limnología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico City, Mexico;*

⁸ *Unidad de Microbiología Molecular, Instituto de Investigaciones Biológicas Clemente Estable (MEC), Montevideo, Uruguay;*

⁹ *Instituto de Geología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad Universitaria, Mexico City, Mexico*

Maritime Antarctica and the Antarctic Peninsula have one of the highest warming rates on the planet. Temperature rise impacts biodiversity, as well as ecological and biogeochemical functions. Microbes are the most diverse component of the Antarctic ecosystems. They control the flux of matter and energy in these low-temperature, low-nutrient ecosystems. For the collection of Antarctic samples, we face logistic challenges related to unpredictable and severe weather. Antarctic research has therefore focused on the summer, and our knowledge is limited regarding processes occurring during the rest of the year. Here we study microbes' metabolic potential and the transcriptional activity of summer microbial mats and those in the darkest, coldest season, called the Polar Night. In this season, temperature decreases, and light, water and nutrients have limited availability.

We integrated metabarcoding, metagenomics, and infrared imaging to study inland microbial mats, which typically develop in streams and ponds that arise from melting ice.

Our results show that the diversity of summer microbial mats is highly variable among sites. Also, community composition correlates with environmental parameters such as nitrogen nutrients, silicates, and conductivity. Metagenomic analyses provide evidence that these benthic microbes harbor a highly diverse metabolic potential. The differences are particularly marked between autotrophs and heterotrophs and relate to both cellular structure and function. A time-point sampling scheme shows that activity during the polar night is constrained to a few microbial taxa. Infrared imaging results show structural and chemical differences between well-developed and early-stage ice-covered microbial mats.

By understanding how Antarctic microbes respond and adapt to environmental perturbations, we aim to help predict and mitigate the effects of Global Change.